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GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER 957781

WP6 – Foundations

D6.7 – Demonstration Planning and Preparation Activities Report

Responsible organisation	Mytilneos
Contributing organisation(s)	Hypertech, CIRCE, QUE, CERTH, Witside, ESR, MIWenergia, LaSolar, AEM, EEE
Due date of Deliverable	30/11/2022
Actual date of submission	01/03/2023
Type of deliverable	Report
Dissemination level	Public

Disclaimer: ACCEPT is a project co-funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 - Call: H2020-SC3-2018-2020 EC-3 Consumer engagement and demand response Programme under Grant Agreement No. 957781. The information and views set out in this publication are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Communities. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use, which may be made, of the information contained therein.

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Version history

Version	Date	Comments
0.0	18.07.22	ToC share with partners and agreed upon
0.1	1.08.22	First draft version
0.2	19.12.22	2nd draft version, including partial partners' contribution
0.3	13.01.22	3rd draft version, including corrections and partners contribution in Section 2
0.4	09.02.23	4th draft version, complete partners contribution
0.5	13.02.23	First version ready for peer-review
0.6	20.02.23	Revised version after peer-review
1.0	28.02.23	Final version

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Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

BC	Business Case
BoM	Bill of Materials
CGI	Common Gateway Interface
COM	Commissioner
DC	Direct Current
DH	District Heating Plant
DoA	Description of Action
DHW	Domestic Hot Water
DR	Demand Response
EC	Energy Community
EV	Electric Vehicle
HES	Head End System
HP	Heat Pump
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PD	Pilot Director
PV	Photovoltaic
TD	Technical Director
TEC	Technician
UC	Use Case
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

This Deliverable describes the work carried out in the context of Task 6.5 of the ACCEPT project. The goal of this Task is to coordinate and monitor all the activities that should be carried out in all the pilot sites before the implementation of the Demonstration Activities that will be defined in WP7.

The Deliverable focuses on the Site Preparation plan for each demonstration site, describing the management plan, the roles and the whole process of installation and commissioning. The process of installation and commissioning is described with details underlying the differences among all the pilot sites. The workflow for each pilot site is provided, explaining the distinct steps followed from the Level 1 audit (M6-M7) until M27. Each pilot site faced different obstacles and delays either due to lack of equipment, bureaucracy or end-users unavailability during this period. Having provided a full description of the site preparation, the key performance indicators (KPIs) are related to the Use Cases which will be tested in each demonstration site. Finally, a retrospective evaluation of the activities performed is important in order to identify the lessons learnt and share the knowledge and expertise that the Pilot Leaders obtained during this period.

The outputs of this Deliverable and especially the definition of the Use Cases and the KPIs are crucial for the initiation and orchestration of WP7.

1. Introduction

1.1. Objectives and Scope of the Deliverable

This deliverable will define a preparation plan for each pilot site based on the outputs outlined in D6.1. The plan will include activities such as:

- the hardware definition (BoMs)
- the procurement process
- the installation and commissioning process

with explicit roles and responsibilities with regards to the latter activities. In addition, a detailed analysis of the delays, the difficulties and the obstacles faced in that process is provided. Special focus will be given in determining the demonstration activities and the validation scenarios, along with the relevant KPIs, for each pilot site. Taking into account that a big part of the installation and commissioning activities will have been completed by the end of the task, an overall evaluation of the activities performed and the citizen participation will be provided.

1.2. Structure of the Deliverable

This deliverable is structured as follows:

- Section 1 introduces the objectives and the scope of the deliverable, as well as its relation to other deliverables.
- Section 2 details the site preparation plan, describing the pilot monitoring management but also the installation and commission process followed in each pilot site.
- Section 3 demonstrates the KPIs tested in each demo site and relates them to the agreed Use and Business Cases.
- Section 4 provides a retrospective evaluation of the activities and
- Section 5 illustrates the conclusion of the deliverable summarizing all the lessons learnt and the recommendations deriving from each pilot site.

1.3. Interdependencies with Other Tasks and Deliverables

The main interdependencies of this Deliverable to Tasks and Deliverables of the same and other Work Packages can be summarized as:

D2.1: Use and Business Cases to be tested in each pilot site are described thoroughly in this deliverable, which covers the scope of Task 2.1. The responsible technical partners for each Use Case are also indicated.

D2.2: The Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and the datasheet for each KPI are detailed in this Deliverable, which is the product of the work carried out in Task 2.2.

D2.8: More details regarding the Use and Business Cases as well as the Lean Canvas Business Model for all the pilot sites is provided in this Deliverable, that presents the activities performed in Task 2.5.

D6.1: This deliverable, for the work performed under Task 6.1, focuses on defining the loads (energy assets) that will be monitored in each pilot site and the IoT infrastructure.

D6.6: This deliverable, for the Task 6.4, provides a pre-validation of the IoT infrastructure that has already been installed in demo sites and is used under the ACCEPT solution.

The progress and the lessons learnt in this Deliverable are crucial for the whole progress and success of WP7 as well as the fulfillment of the objectives of Task 6.6 in which the deployment of the ACCEPT solution in the pilot sites is coordinated.

2. Site Preparation Plan

A detailed description of the IoT infrastructure, which is installed in the pilot sites, is covered in D4.1 and D4.2, and partly in D6.1.

2.1. Pilot Monitoring Management Plan

The Pilot Monitoring Management Plan outlines the way the pilot partners run the demonstration activities at each pilot site. It answers to the question “What needs to be done day-to-day to keep the demonstration plan up and running”. It should include the standard methods and procedures for executing all tasks successfully. It should also determine job descriptions and responsibilities on every involved personnel along with a reasonable work effort.

The absence of a plan may jeopardize the success of the project. A good management plan helps the project team accomplish the goals that have been set. This can be achieved by:

1. Clarifying the roles¹ and responsibilities of everyone within the project team
2. Splitting the work in reasonable and equitable packages
3. Increasing the accountability and by incentivizing the involved personnel
4. Ensuring that necessary tasks are assigned to appropriate member staffs
5. Bi-weekly Reporting on demonstration plan progress via teleconference

In these bi-weekly calls the Pilot Directors are contributing on the latest developments and will be reporting Pilot site progress to the Pilot Coordinator and the Technical Manager of the ACCEPT project as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Schematical representation of the Coordination among the Pilot Directors of each site, the Pilot Coordinator and the Technical Manager.

¹ The roles will be explained in the very next section.

2.2. Roles in the Pilot Demonstration Management Plan

Installations and the process of commissioning are demanding procedures that should be accomplished by a group of specialized staff in a relatively limited time period. It is necessary in every task to assemble the appropriate personnel and execute the work with high quality, precision and professionalism. Therefore, it is important to clarify roles and declare their activities. Considering the job description of installation procedures, four major key roles have been resorted: Technical Director (TD), Pilot Director (PD), Commissioner (COM) and the Technician (TEC). It should be mentioned that these roles are vastly used in all the installation and commissioning processes, and they have not been defined only for the purposes of the ACCEPT project. Figure 16, in the annex, has summarized all the necessary roles in the Pilot Demonstration Management Plane and more information about these roles, can be found therein, too. Although the end-users are not included to this classification, their participation is crucial for the success of the final operational system.

2.3. End-user(s) role in the process and engagement activities

End-users' key role can be divided into two main branches. The former is that end-users provide their property for installing and deploying the pilot system and, the latter, that they interact with the pilot system during its operational phase providing the necessary data for system evaluation. The acquired data can further be used for exploiting bugs and provoke necessary improvements and adjustment.

Main actions of end-users are:

- To be engaged and interact with project actions
- Feedback useful remarks

End-users Engagement

Main objective of every pilot activity should be the dissemination of project actions and the exploitation of project benefits and future significance. All the company participant members, including the Pilot director and the Commissioners, ought to be polite and interact with pilot users explaining them the aspects of the project. They must be ready to explain the project concept and provide pilot end-users with all additional information such as leaflets, brochures and manuals. It is very important that pilot partners receive the End-Users feedback and use it in order to suggest adjustments and improvements for enhancing project dissemination and exploitation.

Therefore, the whole installation management/work plan should be faced with respect and attitude to:

- Interact with end-users and share with them available information during installation processes
- Receive useful feedback for further improvements
- Introduce end-users to future technological perspectives
- Proliferate pilot sites by attracting new groups of end-users

2.4. Detailed Installation and Commissioning Plan

Commissioning is an intensive quality assurance process. Commissioning starts with the design followed by the installation, testing, operation and maintainance of the equipment. The goal of commissioning is to ensure that the installed equipment operates and that the involved pilots and end-users are prepared to maintain the smooth operation. The detailed commissioning manual was built by Hypertech and was customized for each pilot site including all the necessary information for roles and the sequence of actions in the commissioning process.

2.4.1. The Greek Pilot Site (Mytilineos)

OVERVIEW OF THE GREEK PILOT SITE

The Greek pilot site² is located in Aspra Spitia (Viotia). The settlement accounts for 1,088 dwellings and more than 3,000 residents. The particularity of Aspra Spitia relies on the fact that all the dwellings in the settlement are owned by Mytilineos and all the residents of the village are employees in the factories of the company. A better illustration of the location of the settlement relatively in Aghios Nikolaos is provided in Figure 2. The settlement in Aspra Spitia

² <https://www.accept-project.eu/>

was built by the French company Pechiney in 1965. Mytilineos is responsible for all utility infrastructure in the village such as water supply, waste collection and treatment, and electricity retailing under a favourable pricing scheme. All the end-users in our pilot houses have a strong sense of community since they live and work together for many years. Residents are responsible for all the utility bills; therefore they have strong incentives to improve their energy consumption. In addition, they are very interested in becoming part of a larger European community and compare their consumption to the other communities built within the ACCEPT project. For the implementation of the ACCEPT solution 42 houses, hence 105 residents, were identified as suitable for the installation of the smart equipment and the implementation of the ACCEPT solution.

Location of the pilot sites

Aspra Spitia

Figure 2: Location of Aspra Spitia relatively to the Mytilineos factories in Aghios Nikolaos.

BILL OF MATERIALS

Out of the 63 end-users, initially interested in participating to the ACCEPT project during the Level 1 audit, 52 houses were visited one by one to collect the data which were required for the completion of Level 2 audit. Level 2 audit visits were completed in July 2022 (M19). Out of the 52 visited premises, only 44 were considered as suitable for the installation of smart equipment. In collaboration with Hypertech, the Bill of Materials (BoM) for these 44 residential premises was built by the 19th of September 2022 (M21) and the process for the procurement of the required equipment was initiated. The equipment to be procured can be divided in several categories such as local hubs, smart meters for energy consumption monitoring, smart devices for status monitoring and control, smart sensors for ambient and occupancy sensing. Table 1 displays the model and the units of each device that was bought.

Table 1: Procured Equipment for the Greek pilot site.

Equipment Type	Installation Topology	Device Model
Consumption monitoring devices (used for total consumption and for HVAC and DHW consumption)	Clamp Meters	Z-Wave Plus Aeotec Clamp Power Meter - Three Clamps (60A)
	DIN Rail Equipment	Z-Wave Qubino Smart Meter ZMNHTD1 Plus
	Smart Plug	Qubino Smart Plug 16A
HVAC control	Plug n' Play gateway	Universal IR Air Conditioner to WiFi (ASCII) Interface (INWMPUNI001I000)
DHW control	DIN Rail Equipment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ICT 40A 2NO 240VAC 50Hz MO

Equipment Type	Installation Topology	Device Model
		contact <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ICT 25A 2NO 230...240V 50Hz MO contact ICT 16A 2NO 230 MO contact
Indoor ambient sensing	Plugged device	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aeon Labs Multisensor 6 - Z-Wave Plus (Temperature - Humidity - Light Sensor - Presence)
Gateway for data collection	Plugged device next to the router	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raspberry Pi 4 Model B 2GB Official Raspberry Pi 4 Model B Black Case Raspberry Pi 4 Official Power Supply 5.1V 3.0A (White) Z-Wave Z-Wave. Me RaZberry 2 Module Integral microSDHC memory card 32 GB MSDHC U3 CL10 V3 Aeotec Range Extender

The procurement stage lasted one and a half months due to small delays coming from all the involved stakeholders in the process. In general, the procurement processes in big companies may take longer than expected, due to longer procurement processes that include multiple internal approvals. In the case of Mytilineos, the ideal supplier had to be identified and approved by the CEO. Then, there was a delay from the supplier, MobileHome, in creating an offer for the whole packet of the equipment. The quote for the equipment was received around middle of M22 (October 2022) and the expense was approved by the CEO by the end of M22. The contract for the procurement of the equipment was then drafted by Mytilineos' procurement and legal department. The final contract between Mytilineos and our supplier was signed in M23 (November 2022).

DEPLOYMENT PLAN

In parallel, the deployment plan for each pilot site was created by Hypertech. A deployment plan contains all the information needed for the proper execution of the installation and commissioning processes. More specifically, it enlists the equipment to be installed in each pilot site, with details about the quantities of each device and the topology of installation. All the necessary details about the installation of each device are also provided along with the estimated duration of the installation. The deployment plan also assigns each installation activity to a specific role. Lastly, all the necessary details about the commissioning are given. More precisely, information about the load type, the name of the device in the IoT network, the load type (HVAC, DHW, total energy metering etc) etc. In the Greek pilot site, the roles for the installation and commissioning were defined as:

- Pilot Director: Georgia Roussou (Mytilineos)
- Technical Director: Hypertech IML team
- Commissioner: Charalambos Toubexis, Nick Kaftantzis (MobileHome)
- Technician: Stavros Drouzas (TEKNA)

Having scrutinized the deployment plan and having analyzed the job needed to be done by the technician, the company which operates in the settlement of Aspra Spitia started to prepare its offer in M23 (November 2022). The selected technician has been running day-to-day operations in the settlement the past 10 years and he knows by heart the particularities of each electrical panel. At the same time, he is a trusted party within the community of Aspra Spitia which was proved crucial for building trust with the participants. This trust was significant for

installation of the smart meters that monitor the total consumption, especially the three-phase smart meters. The installation of a three-phase smart meter requires digging of the wall in order to pass through cables that are connected outside of the circuit panel as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: The circuit panel before (a) and after (b) the installation of a three-phase smart meter.

All the smart devices delivered to Protergia’s office in Athens in December 2022 (M24). TEKNA sent us their offer for the installation in M24. A timeframe for all the actions that occurred during the procurement stage is provided in Table 2. It should be pointed out the collection of data for the Level 2 audits started in M16 (April 2022) and the BoM for ten premises was completed in M18 (June 2022). These dates are not included in the timeframe for the shake of simplicity.

Table 2: Timeframe for the procurement and installation process in Aspra Spitia.

Action	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26
Collection of data from pilot houses								
Bill of Materials								
Approval for the expense								
Sign contract with the supplier								
Delivery of the procured equipment								
Creation of the deployment plan								
Training for the installation and commissioning processes								

Action	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26
Beginning of installation and commissioning								
End of installation and commissioning								

Hypertech organized a training in order to guide the Pilot Director and the Commissioners through the whole process of installation and commissioning, before the settlements were visited. The training was planned for the beginning of January 2022 (M25) and all the involved stakeholders in this process were present having a first contact with the actual equipment. As presented in Table 2, the process of installation and commissioning started in January (M25). During the first day, a health and safety plan was composed and signed by us and MobileHome, our partners in the whole process. Each installation process was planned to last 3 up to 4 hours. The Household Managers allowed to visit the houses the morning and the evening respecting the factory shifts. The available slots when the houses could be visited were two, between 9 am and 12 pm and between 5 pm and 8 pm. Two installations per day were planned and one week was kept with many vacant slots to accommodate all the postponed visits. The whole process was completed on the 10th of February 2023 (M26).

2.4.2. The Spanish Pilot Site (La Solar)

OVERVIEW OF THE PILOT SITE

The Spanish pilot site³ is located in Murcia Region, Southeast Spain (see Figure 4). Participants were chosen from members of LaSolar Coop. which are spread among this area. A total of 55 users were selected for the project before the first Level audit was conducted. After the second Level audit, the number of users was narrowed down to 40 due to the characteristics of the dwellings and the compatibility of the smart devices with the home appliances. Finally, one of the pre-selected users left the Coop and the final number of end-users for the Spanish Pilot Site is 39. The goal in these premises is to obtain flexibility from the following appliances:

- PV installations.
- DHW tanks (electric).
- HVAC systems.

³ <https://www.accept-project.eu/>

Figure 4: Location of the Spanish Pilot site

BILL OF MATERIALS

The first task after the selection of the final users was the preparation of the bill of materials (BoM) that was performed by Hypertech. In this document, the devices to be installed in each one of the dwellings was specified. After some exchange of email between Hypertech, La Solar and MIWenergia, a preliminary version was agreed in order to proceed with the equipment purchase. The Spanish pilot partners then asked for tenders in order to obtain the best offer taking into consideration the price of the equipment, the location of the supplier and the time of delivery. Most of the equipment was purchased before the end of July (M19) and received at the beginning of September (M21).

In September, Hypertech developed and delivered to the Pilot Director and Commissioner, the deployment plan for each one of the dwellings. However, a new device to measure Air Quality was incorporated to some of the users' premises thus a new purchase was made and the deployment files needed to be incorporated. By the end of October (M22) all equipment was finally received.

In Table 3, the smart devices are listed that were procured and planned to be deployed.

Table 3: Procured Equipment for the Spanish pilot site.

Equipment Type	Installation Topology	Device Model
Consumption/production monitoring devices (can be further used as HVAC or DHW control)	Clamp Meters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aeotec Home Energy Meter Gen5 Shelly EM
	DIN Rail Equipment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Z-Wave Qubino Smart Meter ZMNHTD1 Plus

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Z-Wave Qubino 3-Phase Smart Meter ZMNHXD1
	Smart Plug	Qubino Smart Plug 16A
HVAC control	Plug n' Play gateway	Universal IR Air Conditioner to Home Automation Interface
	Device integrated gateway	Brand-specific IntesisBox AC-WMP-1 (Exact model dependent on the HVAC brand)
Indoor ambient sensing	Plugged device	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aeon Labs Multisensor 6 - Z-Wave Plus Eurotronic Air Quality Sensor Z-Wave Plus (VOC Sensor)

DEPLOYMENT PLAN

Roles in the deployment plan for the Spanish Pilot Site:

- Pilot Director: Antonio Soler (La Solar)
- Technical Director: Hypertech IML team
- Commissioner: Pablo Barrachina (MIWenergia)
- Technician: Alejandro Andreu (MIWenergia)

In order to be able to start with the deployment the development of the software to be installed in the SD card of the smartbox (Raspberry Pi) was required. This software allows the smartbox to receive the signals from all smart devices and have the capability to control the home appliances. This task was performed by Hypertech. By mid-October, Hypertech sent the image to be burnt in the SD card and the installation could be planned.

MIWenergia, with the support of La Solar, developed a preliminary deployment plan, considering the constraints that come up when visiting users at their own houses, trying to match the availability of the users with the ones of the technician and the commissioner. Originally, there were planned 3 visits per week although with some "off weeks" to consider holidays, for a total of 16 weeks duration for the deployment. Finally, installations could get started the final week of October and finished the third week of February, lasting 17 weeks.

In Table 4, you can see the planification and the progress in the deployment:

Table 4: Timeframe for the procurement and installation process in the Spanish Pilot site

Action	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26
Collection of data from pilot houses																

Action	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26
Review of Level 2 Audits (with HYP)				█	█	█	█									
Bill of Materials							█									
Ask for tenders							█	█								
Purchase of the Equipment							█									
Delivery of the procured equipment								█	█							
New equipment (VOC): Tenders & Purchase											█					
Installation and commissioning												█	█	█	█	█
End of installation and commissioning																█

Figure 5: Planned vs performed installation process

2.4.3. The Swiss Pilot Site (AEM)

OVERVIEW OF THE SWISS PILOT SITE

The Arena Innovation Community (AIC), which is a residential neighbourhood in the suburbs of Lugano, and Fondazione La Sosta, which is an assisted-living facility located in the city, are the two distinct areas that comprise the AEM pilot site⁴ in Switzerland (see Figure 6, Figure 7 and Figure 8). In the suburban context where users typically own the property, distributed energy resources are more prevalent, and flexibility is greater, the former seeks to investigate the users' acceptance of DR strategies. The latter will examine a city-based setting where users are frequently tenants of multi-storey buildings, flexibility is limited, and acceptance is influenced by both the building owner and the tenants.

The AIC is a suburban local Energy Community (EC) developed according to the current Swiss legislation. The Arena Innovation Community consists of a residential area with 11 residential buildings (single-family houses and multi-storey building with several occupants), a large public pool, the football field building with several office spaces, and a district heating plant with biomass-based heat generation. One 30 kWp PV is installed and it is currently operating, another PV of 60 kWp is planned to be installed from scratch starting from Q1-2023, and a third one, with 16 kWp, will be introduced in the community starting from Q1-2023. Nowadays, the PV currently active is mainly used to primarily supply the pool utilities in summer and the district heating plant in winter. The wood-fired district heating plant not only supplies users who are part of the EC, but in total serves about 70 single-family households, with a total thermal energy production of 2.300 MWh and a thermal power of 550 kWp. The DH within the EC is readily connected to the public pool, the football field building, and 3 residential buildings. To enable peak-shaving strategies, the self-consumption community is further extended with a storage system (50kW/54kWh), which is installed at the Point of Common Coupling (PCC) close to the public pool building. The EC was expanded with an EV 11kW DC charging station with V2G capabilities in Q4-2022.

Fondazione La Sosta is a multi-storey assisted-living residence of 30 apartments (30 residents), 1 community centre, and 1 industrial kitchen. The annual electricity consumption is approx. 60.000 kWh, whereas the thermal consumption is roughly 307.000 kWh. A 150kW HP-based heating system is installed together with a domestic hot water tank and a PV plant of 30 kWp on the rooftop. Approx. 40% of the PV production is used for heat pump (HP) operation, depending on seasonality. Figure 8 shows the facade of the building and the rooftop installations.

Figure 6: Location of the Swiss Pilot sites

⁴ <https://www.accept-project.eu/>

Figure 7: Overview of the Arena Innovation Community

Figure 8: Pictures of Fondazione La Sosta

DEPLOYMENT PLAN

Roles in the deployment plan for the Swiss Pilot Site are:

- Pilot Director: Daniele Farrace (AEM)
- Technical Director: Hypertech IML team
- Commissioner: Riccardo Toffanin (AEM)
- Technician: Arnoldo Storni (AEM)

During the Level 1 survey, 18 buildings (some with multiple apartments) were considered for inclusion in the project as residential assets. This number was narrowed down to 6 buildings for Level 2 surveys, and, eventually, reduced to 2 buildings (AEM104 e AEM125). AEM113, AEM115, and AEM116 were excluded from the project due to their connection to the district heating system, which already provides for their space heating and domestic hot water needs through the biomass plant, leaving these buildings without any controllable electric loads. Although

AEM108 and AEM104 are equipped with an air-to-water heat pump, these units are old and not equipped with smart grid ready technology. It was decided to exclude AEM108 from the project, but to include AEM104 as it has a better potential for what-if flexibility scenarios due to its larger size.

Nonetheless, despite only two residential buildings being included in the project, the total number of occupants, 33, is in line with the project objective. The assets are included with the following purposes:

- AIC - AEM104 (3-apartment building): monitoring the consumption of the 11 kWth heat pump for what-if scenarios of demand response.
- Fondazione La Sosta - AEM125 (30-apartment building): controlling the central heating heat pumps by managing the secondary space heating pump.

Moreover, several district assets are included in the project with the following flexibility objectives:

- AIC - district heating: managing the hydraulic pump of the distribution network by varying the district heating supply temperature.
- AIC - V2X charger: controlling the EV 11kW DC charging station and the related car sharing vehicle exploiting the V2G capabilities. Please note that, as the charger was installed in Q4-2022, this is an addition to the project, not originally included in the DoA.
- AIC - district battery and PV plants: improving self-consumption in the energy community.

The collection of data from the pilot sites was completed in between Sep 2021 (M9) and Dec 21 (M12). After this phase, the results of the Level 2 surveys were reviewed in collaboration with Hypertech in Dec 2021 and Jan 2022 (M12 and M13).

AEM's grid is already equipped with smart meters, but it was necessary the development of an interface for simple and secure data access by the technical partners. This process is very lengthy as it lasts for 16 months from February 2022 (M14) to May 2023 (M29), but it was a major update in the communication infrastructure of the company required for granting access to smart meters and sensor measurements for the project.

The definition of requirements (IoT, communication protocols, software and hardware, etc.) for the district assets started in July 2022 (M19) and is still ongoing. This task has proven to be very long, as the assets of the Swiss pilot site are very diverse in terms of technology and size. This requires the involvement of third parties who are responsible for (all or part of) the various systems. The main topic of discussion is the protocols for communication and control and how to interface the system with ACCEPT solutions. In addition, complex industrial systems require a tailor-made approach, which is different in each case. This is a slow process due to the need to build up know-how and coordination with several actors (both internal and external to the project). This part is expected to be completed in May 2023 (M29).

This task will be followed by the bill of materials and delivery of the procured equipment (from M27 to M29). AEM does not anticipate any major delays due to the use of off-the-shelf products and the company's lean bureaucracy. Finally, the installation and commissioning phase will start in May 2023 (M29) and is expected to be completed in August 2023 (M32). This phase involves the final setup of the communication system (for monitoring and control by the technical partners), the physical installation of equipment where required, and the subsequent commissioning of the equipment/communication.

Due to the diversity of the AEM pilot sites, most of which are complex industrial sites (industrial programmable logic controller PLC with complex logic) requiring the involvement of third parties and customised solutions, variations are expected, with the residential sites (AEM104 and AEM125) expected to progress faster than the district sites. For example, the communication protocol for AEM125 – La Sosta was agreed between the third party managing the system and the technical partners. This protocol, called Common Gateway Interface – CGI, requires a setup-and-trial phase by the third party to allow for remote control of the hydraulic pump. This system has been already created, and the remote control of the heating system is currently being tested by AEM. Moreover, sensors compatible with the data ingestion platform have been identified (Netatmo's Smart Indoor Air Quality Monitor) and are currently being tested in AEM's office, before proceeding with the following phases (BoM and procurement of equipment) at the La Sosta building. Table 5 summarizes the plan for the preparation and deployment.

Table 5: Timeframe for the procurement and installation process in the Swiss Pilot site

Action	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32
Collection of data from pilot sites																								
Review of Level 2 surveys (with HYP)																								
Development of web interface / data ingestion (with third party)																								
Definition of requirement for district assets (with tech and external partners)																								
Bill of Materials (BoM)																								
Delivery of the procured equipment																								
Installation and commissioning phase																								

2.4.4. The Dutch Pilot Site (ESR)

OVERVIEW OF THE DUTCH PILOT SITE

The Dutch pilot site⁵ (see Figure 9) consists of the ecological neighbourhood Eva-Lanxmeer in Culemborg which was developed in the period 1995-2005 and was built in different stages. Therefore, the houses differ stage by stage making the comparison difficult and selecting houses for the project complicated. On the other hand, all households are very much aware of the climate crises and are already cooperating in cooperatives in one way or the other. So, the idea behind ACCEPT was not new to them.

A total of 49 users were selected for the project before the first Level audit was conducted. After this audit, the number of users was narrowed down to 38 due to the characteristics of the dwellings and the compatibility of the smart devices with the home appliances. Due to the request of a minimum of 40 users, an extra round was held to select users from houses, which resembled the houses which passed the Level 1 audit. Therefore, the total number of houses currently is 45. The goal in these premises, is to obtain flexibility from the following appliances:

- PV installations
- DHW tanks and boosters (electric).

⁵ <https://www.accept-project.eu/>

Figure 9: Location of the Dutch Pilot site

BILL OF MATERIALS

In order to boost the user opt-in in the ACCEPT project, we have decided to try and include more loads in the trials than the above mentioned. We'll do this through the use of smart plugs. Whether the appliances contribute to ACCEPT or not. This way the users can check the usage of electricity of more appliances than the heavy users which are interesting for the project and they are more willing to cooperate in ACCEPT.

The current progress stage with regards to the deployment of infrastructure at the households in the Dutch pilot, Level 2 audits have been filled in and are currently being analysed/assessed for the creation of suitable Bills of Materials (BoMs) to continue with ordering and installing equipment at the households.

Originally the intention was to invest/co-fund the purchase and installation of a district-level BESS with 2nd life batteries. In the near future a lot of these batteries will come available to the market and we thought it was a very good idea to be prepared for this development. The battery project was also meant to make the usage of locally produced solar energy more worthwhile for loading local EV's. Recently the cooperative decided not to proceed with the investment. For this decision they made a research with all available 15-minute-data from about three and a half year about electricity production and loading the EV's at this location. They simulated the usage of a battery with a loss of 20% by the battery for all kWh which passes the battery. This percentage is widely discussed but seems a minimum one. For the whole tested period this gave a negative result of the business case. The main reason was that the mentioned 20% loss could have been sold to the grid. Also the difference between the price received by loading the EV's via the battery or by buying electricity from the grid was lower than expected.

An interesting development is about the district heater. Currently we investigate the possibility of preheating houses in the early morning to prevent the use of gas and expensive electricity when all users wake up and start using heat/hot tap water.

DEPLOYMENT PLAN

Roles in the deployment plan for the Dutch Pilot Site:

- Pilot Director: Arjen Schamhart (ESR)
- Technical Director: Hypertech IML team
- Commissioner: Alexander van Setten (ESR)
- Technician: to be decided

The deployment was delayed due to internal discussions in the Netherlands. The main reason for this was the intention for a preparation period after the ACCEPT project. This intention had to do with the development of a sustainable solution during the ACCEPT project which could be further developed after the project. For this purpose, it was planned to work with Dutch consultants on a Dutch cloud solution, which was intended to be connected to the ACCEPT cloud platform. During 2022, it was found out, that this was not possible within the timeframe of ACCEPT. Therefore, there was a return to the original plan of ACCEPT with the Level 1 and 2 audits. Currently, these audits are being processed by Hypertech. BoM is expected to be received in March 2023. Installation of the equipment is planned for April - May 2023.

3. Detailed Plan of Demonstration Activities across all ACCEPT Pilot Sites

The problems faced during the installation and commissioning process in all the pilot sites, helped the pilot leaders understand better the difficulties in controlling all the initially defined data assets. Moreover, constant communication and engagement with the end-users was required in order to plan the suitable slots for the installation. This helped the Pilot Leaders to collect useful feedback and better understand the needs of their participants. Having collected this experience, all the four Pilot Leaders and the Solution Providing Partners discussed the KPIs⁶ which will be tested in the demo sites. Table 6 illustrates the final list of the KPIs tested in all the four demo sites. Under each pilot site, cells have been highlighted in green for each applicable KPI.

Table 6: KPIs to be tested in each pilot site (the ones in green are the ones that will be tested at each pilot).

ID	Name	Greek	Spanish	Swiss	Dutch
AE-01	Perceived annoyance from home control automation				
AE-02	Conscious acceptance of Smart Home control automation				
AE-03	Citizen time spent on ACCEPT app				

⁶ More information on the KPIs can be found in the deliverable D2.2 and D2.4.

ID	Name	Greek	Spanish	Swiss	Dutch
AE-04	Citizen satisfaction				
AE-05	Market actor time spent on ACCEPT app				
AE-06	Net Promoter Score				
EC-01	Payback for citizens				
EC-02	Payback for energy community				
EC-03	Residential energy cost reduction				
BU-01	Number of consumers engaged				
BU-02	Number of consumers reached				
BU-03	Willingness to pay				
BU-04	Business plans for how many different roles for market actors/communities				
BU-05	Good practices on community creation				
SR-01	Number of data security incidents				
SR-02	Mean-Time-to-Detect of security incidents				
SR-03	ACCEPT solution downtime				
ER-01	Increase of self-sufficiency at the energy community level				
ER-02	Increase of self-consumption at the community level				
ER-03	Achievable demand flexibility				
ER-04	Achievable peak load reduction				
ER-05	Increase in Flexibility potential				
ER-06	Maximum Hourly Deficit improvement				
ER-07	Number of DR actions sent per user/building/pilot				
ER-08	Energy consumption reduction				

ID	Name	Greek	Spanish	Swiss	Dutch
MR-01	Comfort degradation for flexibility delivery				
MR-02	Model Accuracy				

3.1. The Greek Demo Site (Mytilineos)

Table 7 relates the Use Cases tested in Aspra Spitia with the relevant KPIs as described in Table 6. Since data from domestic PV production is not available in the Greek pilot site, the UC2⁷ will be modified. Virtual Energy Storage Optimisation will only perform optimal scheduling for the operation of the HVAC and the DHW tanks in the residences where these data assets are obtained as opposed to the other three pilot site which provide data from their PV installations.

Table 7: The Use Cases tested in the Greek pilot site related to the KPIs (the ones in green are the ones that will be tested at the Greek pilot).

ID	Name	Greek	KPIs
UC1	Metering & Sensor Energy Data		SR-01, SR02, SR-03
UC2*	Virtual Energy Storage optimisation		EC-03, ER-04, ER-08
UC3	Consumer demand-side flexibility forecasting		ER-03, ER-04, ER-05
UC4	Demand elasticity profiling-forecasting-aggregation		AE-05, MR-01, MR-02
UC5	Intra-day district-level DER flexibility management		
UC6	Day-ahead smart charging flexibility quantification		
UC7	Community-level P2P flexibility		
UC8	Participation in explicit Demand Response schemes		ER-07, AE-03
UC9	Participation in implicit Demand Response schemes		ER-07, AE-01, AE-02, AE-03
UC10	Community flexibility bundling for local congestion management service		
UC11	Retailer day-ahead optimal pricing configuration		MR-02, EC-01, EC-02
UC12	Optimal scheduling and operation of heating generation		

⁷ Further information on the Use Cases can be found in the deliverable D2.1.

ID	Name	Greek	KPIS
UC13	Increase self-consumption at local level		
UC14	Active Citizen and LEC Engagement		AE-01, AE-02, AE-04, AE-06, BU-01, BU-02, BU-03

Table 8: The Business Cases tested in the Greek pilot site related to the KPIS. provides a good relation between the Business Cases⁸ and the KPIS tested in the Greek pilot site.

Table 8: The Business Cases tested in the Greek pilot site related to the KPIS (the ones in green are the ones that will be tested at the Greek pilot).

ID	Name	Greek	KPIS
BC2	Energy Community as an Energy Service Company (ESCO) offering energy management services		BU-02, BU-04, BU-05
BC3	Energy Community as an Energy Service Company (ESCO) facilitating P2P flexibility trading (shadow administration).		BU-04, EC-03, EC-02

Due to delays in the installation and commissioning process in parallel with the refinement of the C-App (based on feedback received by the users during the pre-validation and beta-testing phase), the Demonstration Activities timeframe has also been slightly shifted. Demonstration Activities in the Greek pilot site are expected to start on March (M27), when the BIML will be able to provide data directly to the C-App.

3.2. The Spanish Demo Site (La Solar)

Table 9 relates the Use Cases to be tested in the Spanish Demo Site, as stated in D2.1, with the relevant KPIS as described in Table 6.

Table 9: The Use Cases tested in the Spanish pilot site related to the KPIS (the ones in green are the ones that will be tested at the Spanish pilot).

ID	Name	Spanish	KPIS
UC1	Metering & Sensor Energy Data		SR-01, SR02, SR-03
UC2	Virtual Energy Storage optimisation		
UC3	Consumer demand-side flexibility forecasting		ER-03, ER-04, ER-05
UC4	Demand elasticity profiling-forecasting-aggregation		AE-05, MR-01, MR-02
UC5	Intra-day district-level DER flexibility management		

⁸ Further information on the Business Cases can be found in the deliverable D2.1.

ID	Name	Spanish	KPIs
UC6	Day-ahead smart charging flexibility quantification		
UC7	Community-level P2P flexibility		
UC8	Participation in explicit Demand Response schemes		ER-07, AE-03
UC9	Participation in implicit Demand Response schemes		ER-07, AE-01, AE-02, AE-03
UC10	Community flexibility bundling for local congestion management service		
UC11	Retailer day-ahead optimal pricing configuration		MR-02, EC-01, EC-02
UC12	Optimal scheduling and operation of heating generation		
UC13	Increase self-consumption at local level		EC-03, ER-01, ER-02, ER-06
UC14	Active Citizen and LEC Engagement		AE-01, AE-02, AE-04, AE-06, BU-01, BU-02, BU-03

Table 10 provides the relation between the Business Cases and the KPIs tested in the Spanish pilot site.

Table 10: The Business Cases tested in the Spanish pilot site related to the KPIs.

ID	Name	Spanish	KPIs
BC1	Energy Community as Flexibility Aggregator		BU-04, ER-03, ER-04, ER-05
BC2	Energy Community as an Energy Service Company (ESCO) offering energy management services		BU-02, BU-04, BU-05
BC4	Energy Community as a Retailer		EC-01, EC-02, EC-03
BC5	Energy Community optimized operation via P2P flexibility trading		EC-02, ER-01, ER-02, ER-03
BC7	Prosumer engagement		AE-03, AE-04, EC-01, EC03, ER-03, ER-07

Due to delays in the installation and commissioning process in parallel with the refinement of the C-App (based on feedback received by the users during the pre-validation and beta-testing phase), the Demonstration Activities timeframe has also been slightly shifted. Demonstration Activities in the Spanish pilot are also expected to start on March (M27), similar to the Greek pilot site. The detailed Plan of Demonstration Activities is going to be developed in March (M27) and will be included in D7.4.

3.3. The Swiss Demo Site (AEM)

Table 11 relates the Use Cases tested in Arena Innovation Community and in Fondazione La Sosta with the relevant KPIs as described in Table 6.

Table 11: The Use Cases tested in the Swiss pilot site related to the KPIs (the ones in green are the ones that will be tested at the Swiss pilot).

ID	Name	Swiss	KPIs
UC1	Metering & Sensor Energy Data		SR-01, SR02, SR-03
UC2	Virtual Energy Storage optimisation		
UC3	Consumer demand-side flexibility forecasting		ER-03, ER-04, ER-05
UC4	Demand elasticity profiling-forecasting-aggregation		
UC5	Intra-day district-level DER flexibility management		ER-01, ER-02, ER-03, ER-04, ER-05, MR-02
UC6	Day-ahead smart charging flexibility quantification		
UC7	Community-level P2P flexibility		
UC8	Participation in explicit Demand Response schemes		ER-07, AE-03
UC9	Participation in implicit Demand Response schemes		ER-07, AE-01, AE-02, AE-03
UC10	Community flexibility bundling for local congestion management service		
UC11	Retailer day-ahead optimal pricing configuration		
UC12	Optimal scheduling and operation of heating generation		ER-03, ER-04, ER-05, ER-08, MR-01
UC13	Increase self-consumption at local level		EC-03, ER-01, ER-02, ER-06
UC14	Active Citizen and LEC Engagement		AE-01, AE-02, AE-04, AE-06, BU-01, BU-02, BU-03

Table 12 provides a good relation between the Business Cases and the KPIs tested in the Swiss pilot site.

Table 12: The Business Cases tested in the Swiss pilot site related to the KPIs.

ID	Name	Swiss	KPIs
BC2	Energy Community as an Energy Service Company (ESCO) offering energy management services		BU-02, BU-04, BU-05

ID	Name	Swiss	KPIs
BC4	Energy Community as a Retailer		EC-01, EC-02, EC-03
BC6	Heating-as-a-Service Provider		ER-03, ER-04, ER-05, ER-08, MR-01

The preparation of the pilot site for demonstration is delayed due to:

- the complexity of the systems (La Sosta's central heating system, and the district heating system).
- the age of the equipment (residential heat pumps).
- the need to involve third parties that manage the systems (or some of their components).
- the installation after the start of the project (V2X EV charger).

As a result, the start of initial demonstration activities is expected to occur three months later compared to the Greek and Spanish pilots, specifically in June 2023 (M30). The installation and commissioning phase is expected to conclude in August 2023 (M32) for all assets and full demonstration activities are scheduled for the next heating season in October 2023 (M34). To minimize the risk of further delays, AEM is proactively working to complete site preparation well ahead of the next heating season and will accelerate integration testing after the installation and commissioning phase.

3.4. The Dutch Demo Site (ESR)

Table 13 relates the Use Cases to be tested in the Dutch Demo Site, as stated in D2.1, with the relevant KPIs as described in Table 6.

Table 13: The Use Cases tested in the Dutch pilot site related to the KPIs (the ones in green are the ones that will be tested at the Greek pilot).

ID	Name	Dutch	KPIs
UC1	Metering & Sensor Energy Data		SR-01, SR02, SR-03
UC2	Virtual Energy Storage optimisation		EC-03, ER-04, ER-08
UC3	Consumer demand-side flexibility forecasting		
UC4	Demand elasticity profiling-forecasting-aggregation		AE-05, MR-01, MR-02
UC5	Intra-day district-level DER flexibility management		ER-01, ER-02, ER-03, ER-04, ER-05, MR-02
UC6	Day-ahead smart charging flexibility quantification		
UC7	Community-level P2P flexibility		TBD
UC8	Participation in explicit Demand Response schemes		ER-07, AE-03
UC9	Participation in implicit Demand Response schemes		ER-07, AE-01, AE-02, AE-03
UC10	Community flexibility bundling for local congestion management service		TBD

UC11	Retailer day-ahead optimal pricing configuration		
UC12	Optimal scheduling and operation of heating generation		TBD
UC13	Increase self-consumption at local level		EC-03, ER-01, ER-02, ER-06
UC14	Active Citizen and LEC Engagement		AE-01, AE-02, AE-04, AE-06, BU-01, BU-02, BU-03

Table 14 provides the relation between the Business Cases and the KPIs tested in the Dutch pilot site.

Table 14: The Business Cases tested in the Dutch pilot site related to the KPIs.

ID	Name	Dutch	KPIs
BC1	Energy Community as Flexibility Aggregator		BU-04, ER-03, ER-04, ER-05
BC2	Energy Community as an Energy Service Company (ESCO) offering energy management services		BU-02, BU-04, BU-05
BC3	Energy Community as an Energy Service Company (ESCO) facilitating P2P flexibility trading (shadow administration).		
BC4	Energy Community as a Retailer		EC-01, EC-02, EC-03
BC5	Energy Community optimized operation via P2P flexibility trading		
BC6	Heating-as-a-Service Provider		
BC7	Prosumer engagement		AE-03, AE-04, EC-01, EC03, ER-03, ER-07

Due to delays in the installation and commissioning process in parallel with the refinement of the C-App (based on feedback received by the users during the pre-validation and beta-testing phase), the Demonstration Activities timeframe has also been slightly shifted. The detailed Plan of Demonstration Activities is going to be developed in March (M27) and will be included in D7.13.

4. Retrospective evaluation of the activities

4.1. The Greek pilot Site (Mytilineos)

The Management plan was important in order to allocate the suitable residences. Out of the 63 residents filling the Level 1 audit, only 52 were identified as suitable for the installation of smart equipment. Some premises did not have electric-based controllable equipment, some others were not occupied during the whole year and therefore did not have a Wi-fi router. Level 2 audit was important, since even more houses with very old appliances or old electrical panels with no space for the placement of smart meters were identified. Therefore, the list of participants was narrowed down to 44 houses. In the Site Preparation Plan, the initial BoM has to be modified based on the availability of the devices in the market. A close communication between our supplier, MobileHome, and Hypertech was necessary to finalize the BoM. The procurement process was initiated when the BoM was finalized.

Scheduling the visits to 44 houses within a period of 5 weeks was challenging. The strategy was to keep many slots vacant during the final week for many last-minute cancellations. A doodle with the available slots was circulated to all the pilot participants. Several reminders and phone calls to non-responsive participants followed. As a result, a concrete plan was formed for the first 4 weeks before the visit to Aspra Spitia. This initial plan was modified more than five times during the installation process, since many participants gave us a last-minute notice. Due to the location and the fact that Mytilineos is responsible for the maintenance of the houses limited our choice of choosing a technician expert in the installation of smart meters. There is only one company which is allowed to operate as Technician in these presidential premises since its employees have passed all the required hygiene and insurance tests. As a consequence, extra time in training the Technician on how to install the smart devices on the circuit panel was spent, but this fact, had also an added value to the project because the technician, as an already trusted party within the community, helped with the engagement of the users.

During the process of installation and commissioning, several issues arose such as lack of space in the circuit panel for the installation of actuators (that control certain loads in the households), AC units directly connected to the circuit panel and not to plugs such as stated in the Level 2 audit. These disagreements between the Level 2 audits and the actual infrastructure could be either due to mistakes made in the audits or changes made to the loads by the occupants in the meantime between the Level 2 audit and the installation. This led to the purchase of wrong equipment, delays during the installation and improvisations. Efficient communication between the Technical partners and the Commissioning Team resulted into changes in the deployment plan on site leading to successful installations. One house was though removed from the pool of users since the owner had stopped his internet connection, therefore there was no available Wi-Fi router. While the Commissioning Team was performing the installations all around the settlement, one more user left the project leaving us with 42 residential premises.

Presenting to the users the Dashboard of the C-App, only a few days before the visit to their houses, was useful. During the installation, it was explained to the residents what each device measures and how it will serve for the indications on the C-App. Our next goal is to continue this engagement and give to the users a view of their personal data in less than a month. Keeping a constant communication with them and informing them about the progress of the project is important and it will help us to have them engaged during the demonstration activities.

In Figure 10, some pictures of the installations in some pilot houses are given.

Figure 10: Pictures from the installations. From left to right: an ICT device controlling the DHW via a smart meter attached to the latter; a smart plug for the AC units consumption monitoring; a Raspberry Pi Gateway for the collection of data from all the smart devices

4.2. The Spanish Demo Site (La Solar)

In general, the whole deployment process, starting with the Management plan, site preparation (Level 1 and Level 2 audits), and the Deployment itself, accomplished the target to prepare the facilities in the users' premises to be integrated in the ACCEPT IoT infrastructure. The Management plan, with the definition of roles, along with the two-step audits were useful tools and allowed the Technical Director and the Pilot Manager to have an exact idea of the appliances that were going to be part of the ACCEPT solution and prepare the BoM. A good coordination between Technical partner (Hypertech) and Pilot responsible (LaSolar and MIWenergia) facilitated the completion of the installations and ease the solution of the issues that came up during the whole process.

The purchase process started as soon as the BoM was elaborated by the Technical partners and all doubts and comments were solved. This made possible that all equipment was ready before the installation could start and didn't suppose any constraint for the deployment.

Installation on residential dwellings required not only good planification but also took a lot of preparation due to the fact that the visits must be accommodated to the schedule of the users, without being possible to do it with so much time in advance (usually 2 weeks) and sending reminders was an action taken to avoid last minute cancellations (that still happened).

In some cases, there were differences between the audits and the state of the premises, in some cases because the users had made some changes in the appliances (change in the HVAC units, new PV plant, etc.) and the commissioner, technician need to come up with a “on-site” solution with the support of the Technical team that needed to approve and validate that solution. Figure 11 shows some pictures from the performed installations and give a real understanding of the space that the smart devices occupy in the house.

Visits to the users for the installations gave ideas about user requirements and functionalities to be added to the C-App, like including the possibility to program the smart plugs, because several users had analogical clock to control the periods were the electric tank was on and off.

It will be important to keep user engagement to launch a preliminary version of the C-App, even without all functionalities but providing information about the consumption of their premises and appliances. This way, even before the demonstration starts, the users will start feeling the benefits of their participation in ACCEPT project.

Figure 11 Pictures from the installations in the Spanish Demo Site. From left to right: work on an electric board to install Shelly smart meter to measure consumption; Multi-sensor and Air Quality sensor to measure ambient conditions; a smart plug for the AC units consumption monitoring and an Intesis device to control that unit;

4.3. The Swiss Demo Site (AEM)

The preparation of the audits was useful in identifying the assets that could proceed within the project, by narrowing down the number of residential assets and identifying the characteristics of every asset.

In addition, as mentioned above, the need to involve third parties slows down the process due to the need for coordination between the actors and the need to build up the know-how for each bespoke solution. AEM, the pilot manager, and Hypertech, the technical partner, worked well together to resolve any issues that arose throughout the process. Nevertheless, there is a slight delay compared to the original plan, but this does not affect the expected result of the task.

The district heating system in Capriasca Calore posed a challenge as the network had limited electric flexibility and the biomass boiler was managed by the manufacturer, which meant that direct control was not possible due to warranty restrictions. To overcome this, the team explored the potential of controlling the hydraulic pump by varying the DH temperature control. After consultation with the third-party system manager, it was decided to operate on the mixing valve between the supply and return temperature of the distribution network, which avoided direct control of the boiler. It is worth noting that the industrial system operates with a BACNet/IP communication protocol, which requires a dedicated solution currently being discussed with the third party and technical partners.

The V2X charger was installed in Q4-2022, and several actors were involved in its inclusion. Firstly, the Head End System (HES) of AEM needed updating by a third party to enable the correct control signal to be sent. Secondly, since the EV was part of a car-sharing company, connecting to their booking system was necessary to determine the times available for flexibility. The API to retrieve the booking time slots is currently under development, and beta versions have been tested, providing adequate information for the project’s needs. Finally, there have been bureaucratic delays as some technical documents were missing to operate the station for the project’s needs.

From the issues faced with the district assets, several lessons can be learned. Firstly, it is important to thoroughly investigate the flexibility potential of assets and systems during the project. This can help identify any limitations or obstacles that may arise and allow for appropriate solutions to be developed. Secondly, it is crucial to have open and collaborative communication with third-party system managers and technical partners to ensure a smooth integration of the assets and systems into the project. Additionally, it is important to account for any bureaucratic delays that may arise, particularly with the inclusion of new assets or systems. Finally, it is important to consider alternative options and have contingency plans in place in case of unexpected issues to avoid delays in the commissioning and demonstration phases of the project.

4.4. The Dutch Demo Site (ESR)

In the Dutch demo site, we learned a lot about the positive effect of EU-projects. We worked together with many different countries and even more different people, without a physical start due to COVID.

In Holland we also wanted to prepare ourselves for the period after the project finished and tried to reach direct results which could be useful for that period. The past year we realized our ambitions were too high and could not fit in the timeframe of the project. We are very grateful Hypertech gave us the possibility for a second chance within ACCEPT. Because of this we are a little behind on our schedule, but surely will be in time to reach the requested result. At the same time we are very well aware of all learned lessons within ACCEPT. Therefore we started a Dutch project called "[Local4Local](#)" putting this knowledge into a local solution for the coming years.

In our pilot site it was also challenging to find the requested amount of households to cooperate within ACCEPT. The pilot site consists of many different types of houses which makes looking for households, a very time-intensive process. The audits were very useful to select the households which fit in the project and fortunately we were able to opt-in a few houses in a later stage to reach the requested amount.

5. Conclusion

Greek Demo Site - Lessons learnt:

The whole process from the stage of auditing (started in M5) until the finalisation of the BoM and the installation of the equipment (finished in M26) lasted almost two years. The lessons learnt from that process with some recommendation can be listed as:

- For the completion of the Level 2 audit, two visits to the settlement were required. The first and the second visit were realized with 1 year of difference. The fact, that the ten houses visited during the first visit (M16), were considered as 'ready', instead of being revisited to confirm the validity of the original audits, and the BoM was built upon these collected information, led into huge mistakes in the process of installation. More precisely, in many of these houses the set-up had changed and the AC units were no longer connected to a plug but to the electrical panel. Therefore, in the end there was a surplus in smart plugs and a deficit in Shelly smart meters. Even in the houses that were visited in July 2022, for which the installations were performed in January 2023, similar changes were faced in the set-up, since people bought new AC units. A strong recommendation is to plan better the site-visits and make sure that the installations start no longer than 2 months after the Level 2 audit. When site-visits cannot be performed in such a short time-period, revisiting some of the premises to confirm that the information in the audit are still valid is recommended.
- Another important lesson learnt was the delay in editing and signing the contract for the procurement of the equipment with MobileHome. Since the first contract passed all the necessary approvals from the Legal and the Procurement Department, there was no further delay in signing the contract for the installation and commissioning of the equipment. This experience helped us learn all the internal legal processes of the company and no further delay is expected for the upcoming actions.
- The fact that only one company operates in the area of Aspra Spitia, limited our options in choosing a technician who would be an expert in smart equipment. On the one hand, the assigned technician was not familiar with the installed equipment. As a result, there was a need for 30 extra minutes in the first three installations in order to train him and show him how to read the connections from the manual of each smart device. On the other hand, the Technician had a perfect knowledge of how difficult the installation in each electrical panel will be since he knew by heart the houses after working there for so many years. This helped us modify the deployment plan way before going to the house. Moreover, residents knew Stavros in person and there was a trust between them. This was crucial for us to perform the installations since they happily gave us permission to make changes to their electrical panel. Changes were even more invasive for the installation of the three-phase smart meters, since the Technician had to dig up the wall to pass through the cables of the smart meter as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: An example of digging that was necessary for the installation of a three-phase smart meter.

- Another difficulty which was faced in the first installation was the lack of experience with the real systems and the real devices. As a consequence, the first installation took more than 5 hours which annoyed the resident. One recommendation is to build a demo deployment plan and perform a demo installation and commissioning in an office before visiting the real pilot sites in order to gain experience in such installations prior to visiting actual households.
- Even though the devices are small and require only a small spot on a shelf, several residents were annoyed from their look. To solve this problem, several smart sensors were taped on the wall with double-sided tapes, as shown in Figure 13. In addition to that, the devices needed access to a plug. The residences in Aspra Spitia have been built having only one plug per room. Therefore, extra plug-extendors were brought and left in the houses since the gateway, the sensors and the Intensis IR are plug-in devices.
- Finally, keeping slots for one week extra was proved mandatory, since there were several cancellations due to a COVID incident in the house or a last-minute business trip. All these cancellations were allocated to one available slot during the 5th week.

Figure 13: Smart sensor taped on the wall.

Spanish Demo Site - Lessons learnt:

- Good and accurate 1st Level and 2nd Level Audit and Coordination with the Technical team is fundamental to avoid issues and save time.
- Purchase: start the purchase and order the equipment as soon as possible to mitigate possible delays.
- Planification: be conservative with the number of installations per week and the estimated time for each one, users have their lives besides the project and the pilot managers need to accommodate to that. Plan visits with no more than 2 weeks in advance and send reminders before going to the premises.
- Deployment plans: the documents sent by the Technical team that summarizes the steps for installation and commissioning, avoid issues and facilitates commissioning work. It's important to check it before going to the user's place to have a clear estimation of deployment time.

- Carry extra equipment in case there are faulty devices or changes in the appliances compared to the 2nd Level Audit.
- Experience helps for commissioners/technician with no previous experience, workshops with Technical team help to ease the learning curve. Figure 14 demonstrates how the workshops with the Technical Team helped the Commissioning Team to perform complex installations such as the placement of the smart meter that monitors the HVAC consumption.

Figure 14: An example of work to install a Shelly smart meter inside an AC unit to measure HVAC consumption.

Spanish Demo Site - Difficulties/obstacles:

- One user left the Coop thus also the project, it is important to have a wide pool of possible users to cover for losses.
- There were several cancellations and delays by the users. A mitigation action already commented that was taken was sending reminders to users.
- In some dwellings, there were different issues such as lack of sockets, change in appliances or issues in the electric board as shown in Figure 15 (old equipment, lack of space...) that required in-site solutions and made the deployment last longer than expected.

Figure 15: An example of lack of space inside the electric board for the installation of smart meters.

- Some users don't want to see devices, so it was required to hide those devices even though some functionalities were not at a 100% (occupancy for multi-sensors).
- There were several issues with Intesis (HVAC control devices) that required in some cases longer time to commission the devices and in other, a second visit to finish the installation. Commissioner was in contact

with Intesis technical support team to solve the problems but was not possible with all of them, so some HVAC units were discarded.

Swiss Demo Site – Lessons learnt:

- During recruitment, the users showed poor interest and low participation, thus several one-on-one meetings were necessary.
- During project interviews, the users emphasised that the lack of tangible progress is an issue.
- The involvement of third parties slows down the process. Coordination is needed to ensure open and collaborative communication with third-party managers and technical partners.
- A detailed investigation of the flexibility potential of assets with the surveys showed that many residential buildings are equipped with older devices that are not adapt for the project’s needs.
- Industrial systems are complex and require a tailored approach.
- It is useful to consider alternative options and contingency plans to avoid delays in project phases.

Dutch Demo Site - Lessons learnt:

- Selecting households and preparing the audits take a lot longer than expected.
- Audits are very useful in this process.
- In this stage more technical knowledge is needed than expected.
- External decisions have a big impact on the project.
- Future use of during the project developed knowledge, gives more interest in the project by all concerned: personal, energy cooperatives and consultants.

6. ANNEX

For every key role description, its activities and responsibilities are described in parallel with the corresponding competences of the assigned employee. The following material is commonly used in other projects and is not a product of the ACCEPT project.

TECHNICAL DIRECTOR (TD)

Technical Director is by definition responsible for the technical solution. He is assigned to guide the technical teams through every step of installation procedure, interfere with technical issues and troubleshooting. Technical Director should have a unique knowledge of the whole intergraded system and he is also responsible for training the technical staff and propagate knowledge as part of his technical experience to the newly created technical teams. He may be requested to participate in technical staff evaluation and roles definition as well as the general roll out of installations plan.

Main activities/responsibilities:

- Deep understanding of technical solution and system implementation
- Good experience with system’s components
- Deep Knowledge of Installation guidelines/instructions
- Deep Knowledge of each installed device commissioning guides
- Training of technical teams
- Evaluation of technical staff
- Help commissioners and technicians for solving technical problems
- Assessment of delivered installations per pilot site.
- Evaluate the whole installation procedure

Propose improvements, adjustments to technical solutions based on both end-users’ feedback and his own experience.

Competences:

- Excellent knowledge of technical issues, device commissioning and system integrations.
- Familiar with relevant technical projects
- Good knowledge of hardware and software
- Teaching/training skills
- Ability to support technical teams with short response time

PILOT DIRECTOR

Pilot Director is responsible for managing the whole demonstration activities. His role description is very wide and includes all non-technical issues along with managing the technical teams and communicating with end-users. Managing skills and leadership are among the most preferred capabilities of the person that will be responsible for this position.

Main activities/responsibilities:

- Implementation of the proposed installation management plan
- Definition of roles and responsibilities
- Personnel Evaluation
- Assigning roles to the most appropriate persons internally
- Inspection and monitoring of installation work plan and technical teams respectively
- Equipment procurement monitoring and delegation
- Set a communication plan for appointment arrangements with end-users
- End-users engagement

Assessment of end-users' feedback for further system configuration or optimization

Competences:

- Good management skills
- Good in communication and public relations
- Familiar with pilot projects
- Ability to manage and control groups of technicians
- High level familiarity with the system architecture

COMMISSIONER (COM) AND TECHNICIAN (TEC)

COM's key role is to implement the installation and commissioning procedures in every pilot site. Trained and supported by the appropriate TEC, COM's role is to start from scratch and deliver an operational system in every pilot site. While TEC is responsible for installing plug 'n' play devices and sensors for system configuration and validation, COM is responsible for the proper implementation of the commissioning plan. COM is also responsible for the first level support and copes with installation issues. Moreover, COM has a major role on interacting with the end-users and explaining them how the system operates and how they can interact with the data.

Main activities/responsibilities:

- Installation of plug 'n' play devices
- Deliver instructions to technician for hard installations
- Commissioning of all system devices.
- System configuration
- System validation
- Troubleshooting
- Deliver ad hoc solutions when it's necessary
- System presentation to end-users
- End-user engagement and benefits awareness

Competences:

- Experience in device installations
- First level knowledge on system configuration and software setups:
- Basic knowledge on electric circuits and networking
- Strong technical skills
- Good in public relations

Figure 16: Schematical representation of the roles assigned to each Pilot Partner for the execution of the demonstration plan.